

Contribution Of Legal Framework On Student Academic Performance At Higher Learning Institutions In Tanzania

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to assess the contribution of the legal framework governing higher learning institutions in shaping academic performance at study area. The legal framework establishes the rules and principles that guide behavior, decision-making and processes within that context. in academic performance of students at Higher learning Institutions. The legal framework provides a structure which outlines how laws and regulations are organized and interrelated. Secondly, it provides Guidance: It offers direction on how to comply with legal requirements. Third, it provides Standards which sets benchmarks for acceptable practices and conduct. Fourth; it provides accountability which establishes the mechanisms for enforcing laws and holding parties accountable for their actions. The factors which caused the poor legal framework with respect to academic performance such as: poor structure of legal framework, poor guiding and counseling, poor education policies, poor infrastructure, poor standards and poor governance, A survey and observation methods were used for data collection by using questionnaires and interview checklist supported by personal overt ethnography, focus group discussions with a few informants. The Statistical and Package for Social Sciences (SPSS Version 20) was used to analyze the data. The findings observed the challenges of poor legal framework at higher learning institution whereby the academic performance becomes low for students. From the study it can be concluded that much efforts are still needed to enhance effective legal framework academic performance for students at Higher learning Institutions. The study recommends on changes of legal frameworks by empowering the students and all academic stakeholders to understand and practice deeply the formation of students to a positive altitude.

Keywords: Legal Framework, Student Services and Student Academic Performance.

INTRODUCTION

The Higher learning Institutions is a public institution mandated to conducting legal training and academic programmes leading to award different courses. The legal framework establishes the rules and principles that guide behavior, decision-making, and processes within that context. in academic performance of students at Higher learning Institutions. The legal framework provides a structure which outlines how laws and regulations are organized and interrelated. Secondly, it provides Guidance: It offers direction on how to comply with legal requirements. Third, it provides Standards which sets benchmarks for acceptable practices and conduct. Fourth; it provides accountability which establishes the mechanisms for enforcing laws and holding parties accountable for their actions (UNESCO, 2015).

The legal framework has its importance is an engine on looking the total ways of living of students within the institute by preparing the environment to be a good place of living and studying through shaping

forming and transforming the negative altitude to positive of Higher learning Institutions (TCU, 2021). The higher learning institutions are responsible for the coordination of student-related programs at a university, Institute or college (WB, 2019). Also known as a higher education administrator, they help respond to students' needs, direct admissions, collaborate with different departments and plan social programs for students (Mshana, 2014) The higher learning institutions plans and directs institutions activities related to student services. The higher learning institutions should coordinate admissions, health services, financial aid, accommodation and social programs for students (Suleiman, 2020).

Legal framework with respect to student academic performance is responsible to students with the major role on guiding and counseling services (Mhando, 2018). In the counseling is the application of mental health, psychological or human development principles that address wellness, personal growth, career development and more serious problems of

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stress, quarrels, stealing, sexual relations, attempting in killings and suicide). The Counseling is a developmental or intervening process for a human being especially for students and staffs at Higher learning Institutions (MoEST, 2016). Guiding services means that is an activity of directing, watching and monitoring their total ways of living by considering the rules, regulations and by-laws of Higher learning Institutions. Other minor duties and responsibilities social affairs like games, clubs, funeral, religion, relation, environmental, cleanliness, wearings, contributions, visiting, promoting talents, discipline and maturity teaching.

It is true that the most of students are under eighteen and 95 % of students are those who completed form four and joined the Basic Certificates and then continue with Diploma. Only 5 % of students who completed form six are few. Also the most of students are those who get division One, Two, three and 4 D passes depend on the institution and course (MoEST, 2016). With that logic, the most of students of ordinary level performance was low, majority are in matured, children under eighteen years old which need to be helped in aspects of development by being guided and counseled in his personal life and academic life (Kahanda, 2020). The legal framework is very crucial and fruitful for the personal growth and academic growth of the students in all aspects of developments. The legal framework is sharper and changer of mindset of students in their behavioral change. The professionals should make sure the sports, games and counseling services are conducted well. The study observed several challenges in addressing the students' affairs at Higher learning Institutions and came with the recommendations. There was ineffectiveness and inefficient of services delivery to students at Higher learning Institutions in Tanzania.

The legal framework for students confronted by several challenges in Tanzania some include: lack of accommodation, poor support from local community and government, lack trained personals, poor library services, lack of financial education, limited loan allocation from HELB, lack of skills, insufficient resource specialists in guiding and counseling and combined with inaccessible classrooms (Mhando, 2019). A lack of adequate, accessible physical infrastructure (Education International, 2019) Also, a lack of fund from central government, very limited

resources are available to carry out the requisite assessment and intervention processes (Tanzania Daily News, 2021). The impacts of effectiveness and efficient of legal framework on student academic performance at higher learning institution some including: reading difficulties, failure to comprehend information (Mhando, 2019), poor enrollment of students, and poor quality instructions and poor knowledge for required personals (Kahanda, 2020). Several measures have been done by the Government of Tanzania to reduce the problem of poor effectiveness and efficient of legal framework on student academic performance some including: National policy reviews, to increase the skilled labour, financial support, awareness through seminars and civic educations, campaign and curriculum reviews but with little success.

Different studies from various authors have tried to give suggestions and recommendations to solve the problem poor effectiveness and efficient of legal framework on student academic performance at high learning institutions with little success some include: a study by TCU, 2021) focused on guiding and counseling services, (UNESCO, 2015) on career services and financial support, MoEST (2016) on discipline and conduct for students, Kahanda (2020) on the Influence of Regulatory Frameworks, Mhando (2019) on Legal Framework and Student Academic Performance, Suleiman (2020) on legal frameworks and their impact on Higher Education and lastly a study by WB (2019) who focused on relevant curriculum at higher learning Institutions. From the studies from different scholars, the effectiveness and efficient of legal framework on student academic performance are unknown. Therefore, the study wanted to assess the effectiveness and efficient of legal framework on academic performance for students at Higher learning Institutions in Tanzania.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

3.1 Description of Study Area

The study was done at Higher learning Institutions by selecting four institutions namely the University of Dodoma, Mzumbe University, the Water Institute and Institute of Judicial Administration Lushoto (IJA)

This study was employed a mixed research approach by combining qualitative and quantitative research methods in different ways. The reasons for choosing this approach some is that; the Mixed research approach focuses on collecting, analyzing and mixing

both quantitative and qualitative data in a single study; and in combination of those two approaches, it provided a better understanding of research problems rather than either research alone. A Cross-Sectional Research Design was adopted in this study, and the reason that, it allows direct observation of the events to be studied and interview of the persons who will be involved in the events. The targeted population involved the students that at Higher learning Institutions. Staffs which make a total of students and staffs are almost 12,000 people around the Higher learning Institutions. In this study, the unit of analysis was the individual members composed students and Higher learning Institutions staffs who were concerned with academic performance to whole welfare of students were taken at this study.

A sample size is the representation of certain population to provide reliable information of the population (Yamane, 1967). A 95% confidence level and $p=0.05$ will be guided by the study. The formula for calculating the sample size by using the Precision level Error which is: $e = 0.05$ and where N is total population and n is the number of sample size.

$$\text{The formula } n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)} \\ = \frac{1200}{1 + 1200(0.05)^2} = 98.8 \approx 100 . \\ n=100 \text{ number of the respondents.}$$

Therefore, the sample size was 100 respondents.

The data collection methods help the researcher to get information from the field through different approaches of data collection by using primary and secondary data. Some methods of data collection that will be used some are: Questionnaire, Interview, Focus Group Discussion and Observations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter presents the research findings and makes analysis and discussion of the findings with the evaluation of effectiveness and efficient of the legal framework in Tanzania significantly influences the academic performance of students by establishing standards, protecting rights, ensuring resource allocation, and promoting quality education. This holistic approach contributes to an environment conducive to learning and student success. The

findings were presented in the form of information obtained 90 respondents as a sample size which includes students, Staffs, students, local communities, lecturers/tutors street executive officer and religious leaders.

Also the study comprised of 90 respondents whereby 60 were the community members and 30 were key informants. Thus the findings are preceded by the characteristics of the respondents. The data collected from the field during data collection were presented and analyzed critically. The presentation and analysis of the findings were based on the research objectives and questions as provided in this part. The study aimed to assess the effectiveness and efficient of legal framework on the academic performance for students at Higher learning Institutions. The first objective was focused on the structure of legal framework at Higher learning Institutions. The Second objective was to analyses practice of guiding and counseling services for students at Higher learning Institutions. The third objective was analyzed there Standards used to enhance the academic performance of students at study area. The fourth objective was examined that the existing practice of the discipline and conduct for students at Higher learning Institutions.

4.1 The Roles of the Legal Framework on Academic Performance of Students

The roles of legal framework have its significant on student academic performance. During the data collection, the respondents replied that the regulatory standards from NACTIVET, TCU and ministry of education were 10(11.1%), who replied that the relevant curriculum development to realities of getting the pure and practical knowledge and skills which were 15(16%), student rights and responsibilities in the classes, reading, studying, examinations and the good governance through rule of law, accountability, democracy, equality, equity, ant corruption were 20(22.2%) and lastly the discipline measures to be taken to the students who misbehave to be given the punishment were 30(33.3%).

Table 1: The Roles of the legal framework on Student Academic Performance

Roles of LFW	Frequency	Percent
Regulatory Standards	10	11.1
Curriculum Development	15	16
Student Rights and Responsibilities	15	15
Good Governance	20	22.2
Disciplinary Measures	30	33.3

Total	90	100.0
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Source: Fieldwork Survey, 2023.

The data revealed that the regulatory standards known by the most where by rules and responsibilities must be fulfilled accordingly. The legal framework must redefine and return back the services to the students. The legal framework in Tanzania significantly influences the academic performance of students by establishing standards, protecting rights, ensuring resource allocation, and promoting quality education. This holistic approach contributes to an environment conducive to learning and student success (UNESCO, 2021).

4.2 Poor Disciplinary Measures for students at Higher learning Institutions

The disciplinary measures in educational settings play a significant role in maintaining order and promoting a conducive learning environment. In Tanzania, criteria for disciplinary measures related to students' academic performance typically include the following: From the field, the respondents replied that the unclear code of conduct were 15 (16.7%), who replied that the lack of consistency and fairness were 10(11.1%), lack of proportionality were 16(17.8%), lack of restorative practice were 19(21.1%), poor parental involvement were 14(15.5%), poor documentation and transparency were 8(8.9%), unsupportiveness interactions were 3(3.3%) and lastly the poor appeal processes were 30(33.3%).

Table 2: Poor Disciplinary Measures for Students at Higher learning Institutions

Poor Disciplinary Measures	Frequency	Percent
Unclear Code of Conduct	15	16.7
Lack of Consistency and Fairness	10	11.1
Lack of Proportionality	16	17.8
Un Restorative Practices	19	21.1
Poor Parental Involvement	14	15.5
Documentation and Transparency	8	8.9
Unsupportive Interventions	3	3.3
Poor Appeal Processes	5	5.5
Total	90	100.0

Source: Fieldwork Survey, 2023.

Figure 1: Poor Disciplinary Measures for students at Higher learning Institutions

Source: Fieldwork Survey, 2023

During the interview, one of the respondents replied that: “Right to Appeal: Establishment of a clear process for students and parents to appeal disciplinary decisions, ensuring due process is followed. Review Committees: Formation of committees to review appeals and ensure fair handling of cases.”(Interviewee, September, 2023). At focus group session, one of the discussant commented that: “In Supportive Interventions: Behavioral Support Plans: Development of individualized plans for students who struggle with behavior, integrating support services such as counseling or mentoring.

Academic Support: Providing academic assistance or tutoring for students whose behavior may be affecting their academic performance” (FGD, September, 2023). According to UNESCO (2021) argues that by establishing clear, fair, and supportive disciplinary criteria, Tanzanian educational institutions can promote a positive learning environment that encourages good behavior and enhances academic performance. Balancing discipline with support is a key to fostering a culture of respect and responsibility among students.

4.3 The Criteria of Regulatory Standards for Academic Institution

The criteria of regulatory standard for academic institutions play a role to make sure the quality is maintained. From the field, the respondents replied that the need of relevance curriculum Quality for academic performance were 18 (20%), who replied that the teaching standards were 23(25.5%), infrastructure and resources were 17(18.9%), student support services were 9(10%), professional ethics and conduct were 5(5.5 %) and lastly the professional ethics and conduct were 5(5.5 %).

Table3: Criteria of Regulatory Standards for Academic Institution at Higher Learning Institutions

Criteria of Regulatory Standards	Frequency	Percent
Relevance Curriculum Quality	18	20
Teaching Standards	23	25.5
Assessment and Evaluation	19	21.1
Infrastructure and Resources	17	18.9
Student Support Services	9	10
Professional Ethics and Conduct	5	5.5
Total	90	100

Source: Fieldwork Survey, 2023.

During the interview, one of the respondents replied that: “Adequate Facilities: Schools should have safe, accessible, and adequately equipped facilities for learning and Learning Materials: Availability of sufficient textbooks, technological resources, and other learning materials” (Interviewee, September, 2023). At focus group session, one of the discussant commented that: “Counseling and Guidance: Availability of counseling services to support students’ academic and personal development. Special Needs Support: Provisions for students with disabilities or special educational needs. ” (FGD, September, 2023). According to MoEST (2026) argues that in implementing these criteria for regulatory standards will help improve academic performance in Tanzania by ensuring a holistic,

equitable and high-quality educational experience for all students. Continuous evaluation and adaptation of these standards will be essential to meet the evolving needs of the education system.

4.4 Some Challenges facing the Legal Framework at Higher learning Institutions

From the field, some challenges appeared such as inadequate enforcement of laws were 11 (12.2%), who replied that the poor resource allocation were 10(11.1%), poor equity and access were 13(14.4%), irrelevant of curriculum were 16(17.4%), poor disciplinary measures were 7(7.8 %), poor quality were 11(12.2%), poor education policy were 9 (10%), poor management , poor monitoring and evaluation were 8(8.9%) and lastly the poor monitoring and evaluation were 8(8.9%).

Table 4: The Challenges Legal Framework at Higher learning Institutions.

Roles of LFW	Frequency	Percent
Inadequate Enforcement of Laws	11	12.2
Poor Resource Allocation	10	11.1
Poor Equity and Access	13	14.4
Irrelevance of Curriculum	16	17.8
Poor Disciplinary Measures	7	7.8
Poor Quality	11	12.2
Poor Education Policy	9	10
Poor Management	5	5.6
Poor Monitoring and Evaluation	8	8.9
Total	90	100

Source: Fieldwork Survey, 2023.

At the field, the respondents gave the challenges facing the chain of command of higher learning institutions some include: poor accountability among the DOS members were 9(10.6%), poor obedient were 51(60%), entrusts were 13(15.3%) and lack of integrity were 12(14.1%). During the interview, one of the respondents replied that: “Lack of robust mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating educational policies and their outcomes can prevent the identification of areas needing improvement, impacting overall academic performance.” (Interviewee, September, 2023). At focus group

session, one of the discussant commented that: “There may be gaps in the legal framework that fail to address emerging educational challenges, such as the integration of technology in classrooms or support for students with disabilities.” (FGD, September, 2023). According to WB (2019) tries to address these challenges requires a multi-faceted approach involving stakeholders at all levels, from government to local communities. Strengthening the legal framework, improving enforcement, and ensuring adequate resources can significantly enhance the academic performance of students at study area.

4.5 The Criteria of Guiding and Counseling Services for Students at Study Area

The criteria of guiding and counseling services has it important in forming the behavior, career and performance of the students. From the field, the respondents replied that there were comprehensive program structure were 15 (16.7%), who replied that the qualified personnel were 12(13.3%), accessibility

were 11(12.2%), individualized support were 8(8.9%), poor disciplinary measures were 7(7.8 %), poor quality were 11(12.2%), holistic approach were 10 (11.1%), collaboration with stakeholders were 13(14.4 %), confidentiality and trust were 9(10%), proactive counseling were 7(7.8%), evaluation and feedback were 4(4.4%) and lastly the intervention were 8(8.8%).

Table 5 :The Criteria of Guiding and Counseling Services for students

Criteria of Guiding and Counseling	Frequency	Percent
Comprehensive Program Structure	15	16.7
Qualified Personnel	12	13.3
Accessibility	11	12.2
Individualized Support	8	8.9
Holistic Approach	10	11.1
Collaboration with Stakeholders	13	14.4
Confidentiality and Trust	9	10
Proactive Counseling	7	7.8
Evaluation and Feedback	4	4.4
Intervention	8	8.8
TOTAL	90	100

Source: Fieldwork Survey, 2023.

During the interview, one of the respondents replied that: “Lack of robust mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating educational policies and their outcomes can prevent the identification of areas needing improvement, impacting overall academic performance.”(Interviewee, September, 2023). At focus group session, one of the discussant commented that: “There may be gaps in the legal framework that fail to address emerging educational challenges, such as the integration of technology in classrooms or support for students with disabilities.” (FGD, September, 2023). According to TCU (2021) tries to address these challenges requires a multi-faceted approach involving stakeholders at all levels, from government to local communities. Strengthening the legal framework, improving enforcement, and ensuring adequate resources can significantly enhance

the academic performance of students at Higher learning institutions.

4.6 Challenges Facing Guiding and Counseling Services for Students

From the field, there were some challenges facing the guiding and counseling, in the data collection, the respondents replied that there stigma and misunderstanding were 15(16.7%), who replied that the lack of resources were 12(13.3%), high caseloads number of students :were 11(12.2%), diverse needs were 8(8.9%), cultural barriers were 9(10%), limited awareness of services were 13(14.4%), inadequate training were 10 (11.1%), technological challenges were 7(7.8%), parental involvement were 8(4.4%) and lastly the policy and bureaucratic constraints were 8(8.8%).

Table6: Challenges Facing Guiding and Counseling Services for Students

Challenges of Guiding and Counseling	Frequency	Percent
Stigma and Misunderstanding	15	16.7
Lack of Resources	12	13.3
High Caseloads:	11	12.2
Diverse Needs	8	8.9
Inadequate Training	10	11.1
Limited Awareness of Services	13	14.4
Cultural Barriers	9	10
Technological Challenges	7	7.8
Parental Involvement	4	4.4
Policy and Bureaucratic Constraints	8	8.8
TOTAL	90	100

Source: Fieldwork Survey, 2023.

4.7 Challenges of Services Offered to Students at higher learning Institution

From the field, the respondents replied that there poor academic advising were 15(16.7%), who replied that the poor lecturing or tutorial services were 12(13.3%), lack of career services :were 11(12.2%), por guiding and counseling services were 8(8.9%),

poor library services were 9(10%), lack of students organization were 13(14.4%), poor health services were 10 (11.1%), poor game and sports services were 7(7.8%), lack of accommodation were 8(4.4%) the lack of life skills, lack of financial aid were 5(5.4%) and lastly, the lack technology services were 4(4.4 %).

Table7: The Challenges of Services Delivery to Students at higher learning Institution

Challenges of Students' Services	Frequency	Percent
Poor Academic Advising	11	12.2
Poor Lecturing/Tutoring Services	12	13.3
Lack of Career Services:	15	16.7
Poor Guiding and Counseling Services	8	8.9
Poor Library Services	5	5.5
Lack of Students' Organizations	13	14.4
Poor Health Services	9	10
Poor Game and Sport Services	7	7.8
Lack of Accommodation Services	4	4.4
Lack of Life skills and Gender Awareness	4	4.4
Lack of Financial Aid Services:	5	5.4
Lack of Technology Services	4	4.4
TOTAL	90	100

Source: Fieldwork Survey, 2023.

Figure 2 : Challenges of Services Delivery to Students

Source: Fieldwork Survey, 2023.

From the field data the findings observed that the single source of income of institution from fees which is little compared to other expenses and fail to build more hostels. The institution need to find more multiple sources of income in order to improve the accommodation services for students. During the focus group session, one of the discussant commented that: “Concerning with The Academic Advising: Guidance on course selection, degree requirements, and academic planning and on Tutoring Services: Peer and professional tutoring for various subjects to help students improve their understanding and performance” (FGD, September, 2023).

At the interview, one of the interviewee replied that: “Career Services: Assistance with job searching, internships, resume writing, interview preparation, and networking opportunities. The Counseling Services: Mental health support, including individual counseling, workshops, and crisis intervention” (Interviewee, September, 2023). According to Kahanda (2020) comments that the students should be give the opportunity in Student Organizations: Opportunities to join clubs and organizations that align with interests and career goals, fostering community and leadership skills. Health Services: On-campus medical care, wellness programs, and health education. Financial Aid Services: Guidance on scholarships, grants, loans, and budgeting. Housing Services: Assistance with finding on-campus or off-campus housing and resolving housing-related issues. The findings implies that these services aim to enhance the overall student experience and support their academic and personal growth.

4.8 The Existing Practice for Disciplines and Conducts for students at study area

The field data shows the challenges facing the by Laws and regulations enforcement at Higher learning Institutions were described as follows: the respondents who replied that due to the poor commitments for DOS officers were 12(14.1%), who

replied that due to poor corporation among DOS members were 16(18.8%), lack of conformity in daily activities were 18(21.2%), sexual relations were 21(24.7%) and who said that by Laws and regulations enforcement was due to poor punishment were 18(21.2%).

Figure 3: Some challenges of By-Laws and Regulations Enforcement for students

Source: Fieldwork Survey, 2023.

At focus group session, one of the discussant commented that: “Higher learning Institutions is supposed to come back to see on how to help the students because the most of them are young, they

need our cares, directives and dedicate our good examples through deeds and words” (FGD, September, 2023). At the interview, one of the interviewee replied that: “Higher learning Institutions is supposed to have a strong by laws and regulations in order to help the majority of students, also Higher learning Institutions needs to have its own hostels in order to control the behavior of our students”(Interviewee, September, 2023).

4.9 Effects of Poor Sport and Game Guidelines for Students at Higher learning Institutions

From the field, the respondents replied that there poor physical health were 9 (10%), who replied that the lack of mental health were 11(12.2%), poor development of life skills were 12(13.3%), poor time management were 13(14.4%), lack of concentration and focus were 15(16.7 %), poor discipline and commitment were 10(11.1%), lack of self-esteem and confidence were 7 (7.8%), increasing of negative behavioral issues were 8(8.9%) and lastly the lack of creativity were 5(5.6%).

Table8: Effects of Poor Sport and Game Services for Students

Advantages of Sport & Game	Frequency	Percent
Poor Physical Health	9	10
Lack of Mental Health	11	12.2
Poor Development of Life Skills	12	13.3
Poor Time Management	13	14.4
Lack of Concentration and Focus	15	16.7
Poor Discipline and Commitment	10	11.1
Lack of Self-Esteem and Confidence	7	7.8
Increasing of Negative Behavioral Issues	8	8.9
Lack of Creativity	5	5.6
TOTAL	90	100

Source: Fieldwork Survey, 2023.

At the interview, one of the interviewee replied that: the sport and game “The sport and game increase the concentration and focus: enhanced attention span: Physical activity has been shown to improve concentration and focus, enabling students to engage more deeply with their academic work. Improved Cognitive Function: Regular exercise boosts brain function, which can enhance memory, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills.” (Interviewee, September, 2023). In discussion, one of the discussant replies that: “The sport and game help a student to have a Better Time Management, Structured Schedules: Balancing sports with academics encourages students to develop better time

management skills, helping them prioritize tasks effectively. Goal Setting: Sports often involve setting and achieving goals, which can motivate students to apply similar strategies in their academic pursuits.” (FGD, September, 2023). According to Mhando (2019) Incorporating sports and games into the educational framework not only promotes physical health but also enhances various skills and attributes that are beneficial for academic success. Schools that prioritize physical education and sports can create a more holistic learning environment that supports the overall development of students.

4.10 The Strategic Measure to improve the legal framework on Student Academic Performance

The strategic measure of legal framework on academic performance of students in Tanzania through the legal framework, several strategic measures can be implemented. Here are some key recommendations: From the field, the respondents replied that there Strengthening Policy Implementation were 20 (22.2%), who replied that the poor resource allocation were 10(11.1%),

Enhancing Resource Allocation were 8(8.9%), promoting equity and Inclusion were 11(12.2%), Improving Teaching Quality were 12(13.3 %), Revising Qualified Curriculum were 13(14.4%), Promoting Good Governance were 10 (11.1%), and lastly the Integrating Science and Technology in Education were 8(8.9%)

Table 9: The Strategic Measure to improve legal framework on Student Academic Performance

Strategic Measures	Frequency	Percent
Strengthening Policy Implementation	20	22.2
Enhancing Resource Allocation	8	8.9
Promoting Equity and Inclusion	11	12.2
Improving Teaching Quality	12	13.3
Revising Qualified Curriculum	13	14.4
Promoting Good Governance	10	11.1
Integrating Science and Technology in Education	16	17.8
Total	90	100.0

Source: Fieldwork Survey, 2023.

Figure 4: The Strategic Measure to improve legal framework on the Student Academic Performance at Higher learning Institutions

Source: Fieldwork Survey, 2023.

At the interview, one of the interviewee replied that: “Legal Framework for EdTech: Create policies that support the integration of technology in education, ensuring that schools have access to necessary tools and training. The Digital Literacy Programs: Include digital literacy in the curriculum to prepare students for a technology-driven world” (Interviewee, September, 2023). At focus group session, one of the discussant commented that “Review and update the curriculum to ensure it is relevant to local contexts, incorporating skills that are aligned with market needs.” (FGD, September, 2023). According to UNESCO (2021) the ministry of education should improve the legal framework to better support academic performance and create a more equitable,

effective education system. Engaging all stakeholders, government, educators, parents and communities—will be essential for success.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

In conclusion, the legal framework surrounding education plays a vital role in shaping academic performance for students in Tanzania. A well-structured and effectively enforced legal system can ensure equitable access to quality education, foster an inclusive learning environment, and promote the overall development of students. By addressing gaps in policy enforcement, resource allocation, teacher training, and curriculum relevance, the framework can significantly enhance the educational experience. Implementing robust assessment methods and fostering community involvement will further contribute to positive academic outcomes for students. Ultimately, a comprehensive legal framework that prioritizes student needs, encourages collaboration among stakeholders, and adapts to emerging educational challenges will be crucial for improving academic performance and equipping students with the skills necessary for future success. Continuous evaluation and adaptation of these policies will be essential to meet the evolving demands of the educational landscape and ensure that every student has the opportunity to thrive.

Recommendations

Improving the legal framework surrounding education to enhance academic performance in

Tanzania requires a multifaceted approach. Here are key recommendations: The ministry of education should strengthen the education policies: comprehensive review: Conduct a thorough review of existing educational policies and laws to identify gaps and areas for improvement. Alignment with Global Standards: Ensure that national education policies align with international best practices and standards for quality education. The education stakeholders should enhance enforcement mechanisms: clear accountability structures: Establish clear accountability measures for schools, administrators, and teachers to ensure compliance with educational standards and regulations. Regular Audits: Implement regular audits and evaluations of schools to assess adherence to legal requirements and performance benchmarks. The ministry of finance should Increase the funding and resources: Dedicated Education Budget: Advocate for a dedicated budget for education that ensures sufficient funding for infrastructure, teaching materials, and support services. Targeted Investment: Focus funding on underserved areas to address disparities in educational access and quality.

The education regulators should promote equity and inclusion: equitable access policies: Develop and enforce policies that guarantee equal access to education for all students, regardless of gender, socioeconomic status, or disability. Scholarship Programs: Create scholarship and support programs specifically for marginalized groups to promote inclusivity. The employers should Improve the teacher training and quality: strict qualifications: enforce strict qualification requirements for teachers and provide regular professional development opportunities. Mentorship Programs: Establish mentorship programs for new teachers to support their professional growth and effectiveness in reading and studying environment. The regulators and institutions should revise the appropriate curriculum relevance and adaptation: regular curriculum review: Institute a process for regularly reviewing and updating the curriculum to ensure it meets the needs of students and the job market. Incorporation of Life Skills: Include life skills education, such as critical thinking and financial literacy, in the curriculum.

The institutions and quality insurances should enhance the assessment and evaluation: standardized assessment framework: Develop a standardized

assessment framework that measures not only academic knowledge but also skills and competencies. Feedback Mechanisms: Establish mechanisms for providing constructive feedback to students, teachers, and schools based on assessment results.

The government, ministries and institutions should foster community and parental involvement: Engagement Policies: Create policies that promote active parental and community involvement in school governance and decision-making processes. awareness campaigns: conduct awareness campaigns to inform parents and communities about their roles in supporting education. The institutions should establish the student services: counseling and mental Health Services: Mandate the provision of counseling and mental health services in schools to support student well-being and academic performance. Special Education Services: Ensure that adequate support is available for students with disabilities, including individualized education plans (IEPs). The regulators and institutions should make sure the monitoring and evaluation framework is done effectively: Data collection and analysis: Develop a robust system for collecting and analyzing data on educational outcomes, allowing for informed decision-making. Continuous improvement processes: Implement processes for ongoing evaluation and improvement of educational policies and practices based on data insights. All in all if the all mentions welfares above will be considered, the conducive environment of mind, body, soul to be in harmony and relations between lecturer, students and other stakeholders will help to form, sharp the behaviors and environment as a result the academic performance of students will be obtained.

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